

PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL NEOLOGISMS

Rustamova Gulnoza Bakhtiyar kizi

Teacher of the Faculty of Translation,
Department of English Translation Theory
Uzbekistan State University of World Languages
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Abstract. This article deals with neologisms, the way they are created (their etymology), their function in the text, as well as the way how they are translated and adapted from English into French. It will show what are the motifs for some translations (Is it a pure semantic transfer or the text and context have their role too?). Furthermore, we will analyse the main techniques/ways of creating the new words and try to answer the question what purpose they are created with for the whole text.

Keywords: translation, neologism, meaning, adaptation, English, French, Harry Potter.

INTRODUCTION

Translation is all about the meaning, but the meaning is not all in translation. The appropriate equivalent is much more than just the meaning of the word in the source language. It implies all possible connotations which the translator has to include in order to represent in the best way and in the spirit of the target language what is said in the source language. This also implies that the translator has to be very educated in grammar and in metrics of both languages, that he/she has to be aware of the context in which the source language is written, that he/she has to feel the spirit of the target language, and that he/she has to be familiar with the cultural phenomena of both languages. Finally, the time the translator has at his/her disposal to do some translation can also play a significant role in transferring the meaning from one text to another.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Most frequently a neologism is a new, coined word or phrase constructed or invented to assign a name to a new reality. Or as Newmark puts it: „Neologisms can be defined as newly coined lexical units or existing lexical units that acquire a new sense.“ Very often it involves the description of the function of the new word or the function of the new word itself as it is the case with the German word *Auspuff* which is a compound word consisting of two words *aus* „from“ i *puffen* „blow“. The English word *exhaust* has the same meaning and it has been translated by means of the similar words: „1530s, „to draw off or out, to use up completely,“ from Latin *exhaustus*, (...) „draw off, take away, use up, empty““. Both

neologisms have a logical, obvious meaning which contains the original idea of „throwing something out of something“.

But, the new coined words don't always have to have the obvious meaning. Sometimes the creator of a word (the author) has had completely different ideas from those which, at first sight, may seem correct. Such a situation can be found in some neologisms invented by J. K. Rowling for the purpose of her book about Harry Potter. During the interview with J. K. Rowling a British reporter has concluded that the neologism quidditch, a popular wizarding sport, obviously comes from the word quiddity: „now, you obviously got the word "quidditch" from "quiddity," meaning the essence of a thing, it's proper nature“. In spite of the fact that the author:

„was really really tempted to say, "yes, you're quite right," because it sounded so intellectual, but I had to tell her the truth, which was that I wanted a word that began with "Q" (Emphasis added) -- on a total whim -- and I filled about, I don't know, 5 pages of a notebook with different "Q"-words until I hit "quidditch" and I knew that was the perfect one - when I finally hit "quidditch." Yeah.“

In another interview the author added that the word quidditch rhymes with the word pitch („an area painted with lines for playing particular sports“): Quidditch pitch.

So sometimes the meaning of the new word is not so obvious and it can be invented for so many different reasons: it sounds better, it has hidden meaning, it describes the function of the word, it rhymes with another word, it fits better in the text or just because it „must begin with the letter Q“ ...

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A neologism unlike an „ordinary“ word poses a double problem for the translator. Firstly, it is a new word, it doesn't exist in the dictionary so it doesn't have its existing equivalent, which makes the translation of neologism even more difficult for the translator. And secondly, after acquiring the meaning of the neologism, the translator has to decide how to approach the problem of the translation of a new coined word. He/she has very few choices. Or he/she is going to keep the original word, the original form of the neologism in the source language, or he/she is going to adapt the new word to the target language. Both solutions are possible but the second one is quite more sensitive and needs much more attention and feeling for the whole (con)text rather than just for the new word itself. In the case of the second solution, the translator again has at least two options: to translate the neologism or to adapt it to the best solution in the target language.

Neologisms in Harry Potter – Neomagisms

The world created by J. K. Rowling is a world of pure magic. At the beginning of the series the reader is slowly introduced to the strange and abnormal world of wizards and witches that is presented to us through the eyes of the Muggle family – Dursleys, the family where the world’s most famous wizard, Harry Potter, is growing up. The only problem is that he is not aware of it and the reader discovers, step by step, along with Harry, a new world – the world of magic. To describe this world, the author invented hundreds of neologisms which help the reader better understand the functioning of the newly discovered world. The neologisms which can be easily called neomagisms, for the purpose they have, function as a sort of a guide to this magical world. At the beginning of the *Philosopher’s Stone*, since it was meant to be “a story for kids”, the magic is introduced by familiar notions and phenomena: a half-giant with a magical umbrella which he uses for spells, cauldron as a symbol for making potions, disappearing glass... All these phenomena are well known to the reader. But then the words take over the role and help the reader immerse into the world of wizards.

Creating the Atmosphere – Neologisms with the Latin Root or Element

Almost all neologisms referring to the spells in Harry Potter series contain the Latin element. J. K. Rowling studied French and classical studies which she largely integrated in her novels. Hogwarts, the school of wizarding and witchcraft, was created in 10th century, which was the time when Latin was used as a lingua franca.

Many neologisms for spells in the book contain an overt Latin element: wingardium leviosa (eng. wing; lat. arduus “high”; lat. levis “light, not heavy” or levitatio “to float”), nox (lat. nox “night”), lumos (lat. lumen “light”), expelliarmus (lat. ex “out, from” pellere “to push”, lat. arma “weapon”), locomotor (lat. loco “place”; motor “to move”). Some of them are combined with the English words, some of them are just creations that sound Latin.

When facing such neologisms the translator has to take care of several things, not only of translation. First of all, he/she has to understand the context and why the author used Latin root words for spells. Secondly, the translator has to understand the meaning of Latin roots in order to give an appropriate equivalent. Thirdly, he/she has to be aware of “what’s coming next” if possible. Fourthly, the translator has to choose which way he/she is going to approach the translation of the neologisms, and finally the translator has to be aware for whom he/she translates (the public).

Proper Names as Neologisms

The proper name has no meaning. It means that, following the Saussure's theory, a proper name will not produce an image in our spirit which will connect the sound (the phonemes that are a part of the proper name) with reality. On the other hand, nouns do produce an image in our spirit. If someone pronounces the letters CHAIR (in correct order and in correct, in this case, English way) it will produce the image of "chair" in anyone's spirit (assuming that a person speaks English, of course). But if someone pronounces the letters HARRY, the proper name will not automatically refer to some particular Harry or to any Harry in general. That means that the proper name has no real meaning. This shouldn't be misunderstood with the names which derive from some overt origin such as for example Leon which means "lion". That only means that the name itself has a meaning but it is not in any particular way related to a person that carries that name.

J. K. Rowling used neologisms to create the magical atmosphere of the story. Many creatures, objects, phenomena which are invisible to non-magical people, exist there as "normal" nouns. But in creating the story she has coined many new names that are always somehow linked to characters' destiny, or at least they reflect their personality. New names are there for a reason. Every name has its purpose. For example, Remus Lupin is a professor who turns into a werewolf during the full moon. His name comes from the legend of creating the city of Rome where two brothers, Romulus and Remus, were raised by a mother wolf. His last name Lupin, comes from a Latin word for "wolf" – lupus. It is revealed in the story that he was bitten and turned by another werewolf, Fenrir Greyback. So, there is a whole story behind the name, especially if the name is a neologism.

CONCLUSION

In this article we have tried to point out some of the difficulties in translating the new coined word. The analysis has shown that the translator's job goes far beyond the meaning and that the successful translation largely depends on the competence and dedication of the translator. When dealing with neologisms the translator has to be extra cautious since he/she must understand the reasons for creating the neologism and its meaning. Then he/she can get busy with finding the best solution in the target language. In our article we have shown that three compared languages (English, French) in many ways show the similarity in approaching the problem of creation and translation of neologisms. In spite of their belonging to a different language family (German, Romance and Slavic) they

all share many characteristics in dealing with neologisms (the way they are created, the purpose of their creation and so on).

Some differences in translation have also been noted especially in the field of new coined proper names. In our opinion it has had also some bad implications for the further reading of the HP books since some offered solutions for the proper names (such as Elvis for Marvolo or Poudlard for Hogwarts) have had an odd overtone not reflecting in an appropriate way the connotation that the proper name has in the original version. Sometimes the best option for the translation would be to leave the neologism as it is if there is no better solution in the target language especially when it is about proper names. It is not in vain said Nomen nest omen.

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